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DEBATING MULTICULTURALISM AND CULTURAL UNIVERSALISM THROUGH PHILOSOPHY OF LANGUAGE

ABSTRACT

An important theme in contemporary discourse is the idea of multiculturalism. This idea implies the acknowledgment of diverse cultural expressions of mankind and the need to accord them distinct respect and recognition. The opposite of multiculturalism is monoculturalism, or what is more popularly referred to as cultural universalism- the view that a single culture is acceptable to the diverse races of mankind and that this culture represents the aspirations of mankind as a whole. This work sets out to interrogate the idea of multiculturalism and the idea of cultural universalism, as well as the assumptions behind them, to locate how or whether other variables behind the cultural phenomena support them. To do this, it applies a position on the philosophy of language. The article aims to re-examine the claims of cultural universalism and multiculturalism through some claims in philosophy of language. However, the debate on the options for cultural expression could be wider and provide more worthy choices. The work applies textual analysis and critical reflections to achieve these aims.

Keywords: Multiculturalism, Cultural Universalism, Philosophy of Language, Relationship, Multilingualism.

INTRODUCTION

An important theme in contemporary discourse is the idea of multiculturalism. This idea implies the recognition of diverse cultural expressions of mankind and the need to accord them distinct respect and recognition. It can also be defined as “the coexistence of different cultures in one and the same society” (Heinz Kimmerle, 2000:146). The opposite of multiculturalism is monoculturalism or what is more popularly referred to as cultural universalism- the view that a single culture is acceptable to the diverse races of mankind and that this culture represents the aspirations of mankind as a whole. Closely related to this is the issue of the relationship between language

and culture. If the world were to adopt cultural diversity and promote different cultures as expounded by the idea of multiculturalism or cultural pluralism, what are the implications for language use in our world? What is the relationship between language and culture or worldview? Is the meta-linguistic basis of language the same as the meta-cultural view of a people? This chapter aims to (re)examine the claims of the proponents of cultural universalism and multiculturalism through some claims in the philosophy of language,

The work invokes the views of two prominent philosophers of language, namely-Frege (1972) and WVO Quine (1969), to appraise the question of cultural universalism and multiculturalism. How true is the assumption of the Western philosopher WVO Quine that there is ontological relativity in human perception? And has this ontological relativity anything to do with linguistic relativity? These are the focus of my paper. The work takes a critical look at the issues of language and concepts against the background of the current issue of multiculturalism to articulate new ways of looking at the relationship between language and culture. I will borrow from diverse areas as African culture, philosophy of culture, and philosophy of mind, to support my claims. The work will first articulate the meaning of cultural universalism. Thereafter, it will discuss the meaning of cultural universalism. It will then proceed to discuss the implications of both to the philosophy of language.

THE IDEA OF CULTURAL UNIVERSALISM

The idea of cultural universalism is the belief that the entire world should work towards the achievement of an objective standard of conduct and a common world culture. This position is anchored on the belief that there are certain universals that cut across all human cultures and that these universals can act as the basis for a common world culture. Proponents of this, such as Emile Durkheim, George Murdock, Claude Lévi-Strauss, and Donald Brown, hold that there is a universal element common to all cultures and that if we recognize these universals, then the imperative to pull the world towards a common culture can easily be recognized. These universals include: the universal human property of rationality and the universal human property of language. Those who support these positions from the point of view of a universal human property of rationality contend that there are certain categories or a common basis for truth which any developed rationality can attain and thus begin to participate in a common world culture. Immanuel Kant (1781) enumerates these categories of understanding enumerates them into twelve categories, which include Quantity.

Unity. Plurality. Quality. Reality. Negation Relation. Causality and Dependence
Modality. Possibility. Existence.

Maurice Merleau-Ponty (cited in Low 1996:377), the French existentialist philosopher, however, establishes another basis for cultural universalism. Based on his critique of Western rationality, Ponty (Low 1996:379) believes that “rationality always remains to be established and is always partial and incomplete”. Consequently, there is no absolute reason or absolute truth anywhere. Against the position of absolute reason or foundationalism, which has dominated Western philosophy for all these years. Ponty believes that the possibility of rational agreement ultimately rests on the structure of the human body and on the fact that it is similar in all members of the human species and that these bodies depend upon one sole world in a similar way. What we witness in Merleau-Ponty. Therefore, is a rationality that questions rationality or an attempt to establish another basis for rationality, hence another basis for a common world culture. I shall not dwell on a critique of Merleau-Ponty here; suffice it to say that his work offers insight into the logic of Cultural Universalism.

The argument in favour of cultural universalism stems from the point of view of language. This argument holds that language is the basic mode of human interaction, and we can talk of a universal human culture based on the universality of human language. This argument believes that language has two aspects or forms: language as signs and symbols, and language as spoken and written words. Language as signs and symbols implies such human expressions as laughter, crying, nodding, clapping of hands, etc. These forms of language, which are truly universal, imply that we can have a common universal form of human perception, evaluation or judgment. Language as spoken or written word, implies that different languages of the world, which we use in conveying this aspect of language i.e., language as signs and symbols.

CULTURAL UNIVERSALISM AND THE CHALLENGE OF MULTILINGUALISM

Can we talk of a universal human culture in a multi-lingual world? What is the relationship between language as symbols and language in its spoken and written form and how does one influence the other? If we posit the thesis that we can achieve a universal human culture based on certain fundamental human properties e.g., the human language, can we conclude then that the written and spoken language has nothing to contribute in the phenomenon of human culture? And that there is no fundamental relationship between the two? What is the

possibility of cultural universalism in a multi-lingual world? To answer these questions. Let's take a closer look at the relationship between language and the words that represent it. According to Max Black (1970:97):

We cut nature up, organize into concepts and ascribe significances.... We are parties to an agreement to organize it this way an agreement that holds throughout our speech community and is codified in patterns of our language. This agreement is, of course, an implicit and unsalted one, BUT ITS TERMS ARE ABSOLUTELY OBLIGATORY, we cannot talk at all except by subscribing to the organization and classification of data which the agreement decrees.

What Max Black (1970) implies by this is that there is an implicit agreement in the phenomenon of language. This agreement is such that things or facts can only achieve meaning within a context. This context is, in most cases, within the agreement of the speech community. If words achieve meaning only within our speech, what is important is to explore the relationship between language and reality. A view that explains this relationship is provided by the theory of the myth of museum. According to this theory, "language" provides the label for "meaning" as mental entities, but since the labels can be switched, the referent, like the exhibits on display in a museum case, are unaffected by and indifferent to any change of labels. Thus, a thing is fixed, definite and absolute and largely unaffected by the words or language used in describing them. This position is strongly supported by the philosopher of language Frege. Frege (1972) looks at the dynamics of language use and the context under which language achieves meaning and argues that "a numeral or numeral expression is different from the number it represents" by this he implies that "we can distinguish the sign of an object from the object itself, just as we distinguish the name Socrates and the person Socrates". His position implies that language is only an agreement with no ontological relationship with the meaning. Frege argues further that "a concept is not in itself part of language" but "something objective" and makes a distinction between what he calls "concepts and concept words" or *Begriffsschrift* (in German). While concept represents a certain objective reality, the concept-word is the apprehension or representation of this objective reality. Hence, "a concept-word is a linguistic expression; it stands for a concept; it serves as a predicate."

In Frege (1972), therefore, we can decipher three representations of reality: first, the objective, second, the concept and thirdly, the concept-word. The objective or thing in itself is not the concern of this work. The concept is not

a matter for psychology; the apprehension or “a concept is a psychological matter”. Frege, by this position, implies that though man formulates or organizes language, there is no ontological relationship between language and reality. In other words that the human input into language is minimal.

The second school of thought in the phenomenon of language is the theory of ontological relativity. This school of thought believes that language is an inherent aspect of the construction of reality. According to this school of thought, “we have no direct access to things themselves”. Our access is always filtered through and inevitably coloured by the distinctive characteristics of a set of linguistic tools. This school of thought insists that there is a human contribution to reality through the phenomenon of language. This is because, in the view of Max Black (1970), the events of the real world are never felt or reported as a machine world does. There is a selection process and an interpretation in the very act of response. In the process of selection and interpretation, man influences the construction or reconstruction of reality, and because of this linguistic basis for reality, the ontological relativists believe that reality is basically relative and that the issue of objective reality can only mean the objectification of a perceived aspect of reality.

The major debate on the possibility of cultural universalism in a multilingual world can be located in the contradiction between cultural universalism and ontological relativity. If we hold that language is mere referent or, as the myth of the museum believes, that the referent-like the exhibits on display in a museum case-are unaffected and indifferent to any change of labels, we cannot see any problem in the possibility of a universal culture in a multilingual world. This is because the linguistic concept implied would not affect the perceived objectivity. In this sense, we can talk of translating or rendering a particular idea, notion, or value in several languages, without any basic alteration in the meaning. But we know that the notion that language may have no relationship with the referent is faulty enough to be contested. This position is evidently demonstrated in the philosophy of language held by the Ghanaian philosopher, Kwasi Wiredu (1980).

According to Wiredu (1980 :34):

When we learn a new language, we also, to a certain extent learn a new philosophy

for the most part, this goes on unconsciously. But it is part of the function of philosophers to elicit the general concept buried under the forms and

turnings of a given language for critical examination. For this, a certain degree of linguistic detachment is obviously needful though not easily attained.

Against the backdrop of the deficiency in the idea of cultural universalism comes an alternative theory called multiculturalism or cultural pluralism. This position believes that there is a need to recognize different cultural groups or units as different units of cultural expression. It implies the need to uphold cultural relativism in our opinion of culture, that any cultural expression should be judged in itself and on its own merits or standards. Thus, against “universalistic imposition,” a cultural pattern is freely allowed to develop and express itself and dialogue with other world cultures. In line with this, it makes sense to approve the views of Sheila Patterson (cited in Segun, 1999) when he captures multiculturalism as:

A state in which the incoming groups as a whole, through their organization, adapt themselves to permanent membership of the receiving society in certain major spheres of association, notably economic and civil life. On its side, the receiving society accepts the group as a lasting entity differing in certain spheres that do not directly affect the overall life of the society, such as religion, cultural and family patterns, and sometimes in the retention of a mother tongue or secondary royalties to a country of origin.

Multiculturalism explains race relations in several parts of the world, including the United States of America, where it has replaced the age-old melting point theory. According to this theory, the American society should serve to promote the fusion of cultures and ensure that America achieves cultural universalism as different cultural patterns pull their resources together to form a common American cultural pattern. But as we have previously noted, there is often the danger of one cultural pattern dominating others in this exercise and thus an attempt to keep certain cultural expressions in the background, and this has been the case with America. For instance, though we have many cultural worlds in America- the English Americans, the African Americans, the French Americans, the Jewish Americans, etc, the English culture has evidently dominated that dominates the American society.

Closely related to the idea of multiculturalism is the idea of multilingualism. This implies the need to promote different linguistic units of the world as a way of promoting multiculturalism. Given the significant place of language in cultural expression, this theory believes that “language is a cultural

heritage expressive of a world around it". Thus, different linguistic world-views of people should be promoted for the growth of different cultural expressions, especially those that are represented by this linguistic unit. Multilingualism is an ideology that has been previously left to the background until recently, when the idea of multiculturalism has grown to demand a renewed emphasis on language. Hence, multilingualism has grown to become an "integral part" of the ideology of multiculturalism. In India, for instance, the question of a lingua franca to replace English, which has been the official language of the people, led to serious riots after independence. Today, India has accepted different regional languages, and up to fourteen languages are recognized as official languages in India. In Zimbabwe, while English is the national language, Shona and Ndebele are official languages "supported by government and used, whether in written or oral form in industry, commerce, the media, judiciary, in cabinet and parliamentary debates among many more situations" (Matambrofa, 1997). In Nigeria, English enjoys the position of a national language while multiple large linguistic groups such as Igbo, Yoruba, Hausa, Ijaw, Tiv, Efik, etc, are all official languages, and this promotes the ideology of multilingualism. We must, however, note that the message or ideology of multilingualism goes beyond this, that is, the idea of treating every language as national and others as merely official. It implies giving every language equal status to enable the maximum promotion of different cultures supported or promoted by these languages.

MULTICULTURALISM AND MULTILINGUALISM

The predominant thesis in the idea of multiculturalism is the promotion of different linguistic units of the world as a way of promoting different cultural units of the world. But implicitly in this idea is the need to assess every culture as being complete in itself and the need to promote cultural relativity. By cultural relativity, I imply a situation whereby the different world-views of a people are recognized and respected for what they are, i.e. a situation whereby there would be no value judgment of any cultural world, as every cultural world would be considered sufficient unto itself. Given this situation, there would be no value judgment on culture. But this state of affairs would also create some problems for the arts in general and the study of literary texts, especially concerning textual evaluation in particular. For this would lead to a certain kind of immunity in the art. For the art in general, multiculturalism as opposed to cultural universalism would lead to ontological relativity- a situation whereby the world-view of a people is declared as being sufficient unto itself. For linguistic analysis, multiculturalism would pose a problem on the growth and development of

language since it would discourage interaction between languages, as every language would claim sufficiency unto itself. Again, multiculturalism would lead to the problem of translation of texts. This is because in the absence of a central language, a literary text would have to undergo a translation to a major national language to be widely read and appreciated. An example in this regard is the case of the Kenyan writer Ngugi wa Thiong’O, who had to carry out an English translation of a work he wrote in Kikuyu to achieve a wider audience since the latter is not as widely known and spoken as the English language in Kenya. Another problem associated with the idea of multiculturalism and multilingualism comes from the point of view of modernity. Given the level of development of the modern world we can argue that not every language can carry the weight of modern civilization, especially as the items of this civilization is not a product of the culture encouraged or promoted by this language. Other languages that do not have this would need to develop to meet this standard. In many literary works, we are likely to have stories and issues written to reflect contemporary experience, e.g., the modern world of technology, thus it would need a development of these languages to be able to study these texts. For instance, it would be difficult to write and analyse any novel based on an experience with a computer in an African language, as the language is considerably ill-equipped for this study. These are the challenges that define multilingualism about culture.

LANGUAGE AND THE IDEA OF MULTICULTURALISM: TOWARDS A SYNTHESIS

From our study, it is clear that the idea of multiculturalism is, to a large extent, opposed to the demands of language as an important way of promoting world cultures. This is because, as we noted, the idea encourages multiculturalism and, to a large extent, would make it difficult to achieve a central defining language. In this case, there would be no unifying language for cross-cultural dialogue as there would be no linguistic centre or centre point for linguistic reference and analysis. We shall witness conceptual relativity congruent to different aspects of language use and application. There would be no basis for questioning or evaluating any culture, as every culture would then enjoy a form of cultural immunity, thanks to the linguistic immunity supported by this situation. But as we have noted, this development cannot be positive for the development of the arts in general and disciplines related to the linguistic study of texts. Without opening up one language to another, it would be difficult to carry out an insightful study of a language, especially as it pertains to its

relationship with another language. Amid these deficiencies, it becomes imperative to proffer a solution to the problem of multiculturalism by way of establishing a middle ground between cultural universalism and multiculturalism. The solution or suggestion could come by locating culture from the point of view of its relevance to man and man in this context implies the number of people represented, defined and defended by this culture. In this case, all articles or properties of culture would be judged according to their relevance to man. Thus, we would be talking about “linguistic humanism as a necessary derivation of this humanism. Here we can only talk of celebrating any culture or abandoning any outlook, a language based on its relevance. The import of this is that we can then talk of a universal language representative of a large cultural unit while promoting different languages to promote different cultural groups. We can talk of developing an African language to express the African world-view, a European language for the same end, and an Asian language for the same purpose. This will ensure that linguists are not handicapped in their analyses.

CONCLUSION

In this work, I have tried to examine the idea of cultural universalism. I have also tried to highlight the deficiencies in this cultural theory. Based on these deficiencies, I looked at the alternative concept known as cultural pluralism or multiculturalism. I have studied the implications of this theory, especially as it pertains to the world in general, I have tried to proffer an alternative theory in what I called humanism culturalism which by extension implies linguistic humanism in this theory culture or language would be valued on its relevance to the speaking community and other world cultures. It is hoped that my position here would raise more questions and urge more reflections on the question of language, concept, and the idea of multiculturalism.

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